

MECHANICAL ENGINEERING

ANALYSES REQUIREMENTS FOR POWER MACHINERY AND DEVELOPMENT OF THE CLUSTERS FOR INCREASING EXPLOITATION EFFICIENCY MECHANIZED WELL PRODUCTION INSTALLATIONS

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Abstract

In this article developed of a new surface equipment complex at the 7th level of readiness, improved in accordance with all operational (technical–technological, economic, energy, safety, quality, and environmental) requirements of machinery used in the mechanized operation of wells.

Implementation of the complex is expected to reduce electrical energy consumption by up to 45%, increase reliability, extend maintenance intervals, and enhance operational efficiency. Production and installation at industrial and field sites will allow validation and optimization of the design. The work represents a significant step in modernizing surface equipment for the oil production industry and provides a scientific and technological foundation for future high-performance pumping systems.

Keywords: Mechanized well operation, drive-transmission, rope-block-crank system, energy efficiency, load balancing, 7th level of readiness.

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Introduction

The proposed solution is a modular drive–transmission–rotary chain based on a rope–block–crank system [1,6], utilizing counterweights to save electrical energy, reduce mass, and simplify structural design [2,7]. The project establishes relationships between input and output kinematic parameters [5,10], balances cyclically varying loads, and develops models to analyze dynamic forces in load-bearing elements. Dimensional parameters are optimized [3,4] to link the motion of the rod suspension point to the productivity of the well-tubing hydrodynamic system.

The focuses on the development of an advanced surface equipment complex for mechanized well operation, achieving the 7th level of readiness and optimized for technical, economic, energy, safety, quality, and environmental performance. Existing balanced derrick units, which dominate the industry, suffer from low efficiency under varying loads, high power losses, heavy mass, and limited adaptability to high-speed electric motors [8,9]. Addressing these shortcomings requires a new design that reduces friction losses, improves energy efficiency, and aligns rod motion with theoretical profiles.

A work focuses on the development of an advanced surface equipment complex for mechanized well operation, achieving the 7th level of readiness and optimized for technical, economic, energy, safety, quality, and environmental performance. Existing balanced derrick units, which dominate the industry, suffer from low efficiency under varying loads, high power losses, heavy mass, and limited adaptability to high-speed electric motors. Addressing these shortcomings requires a new design that reduces friction losses, improves energy efficiency, and aligns rod motion with theoretical profiles [10].

Task and novelty of the topic: Development of a new surface equipment complex at the 7th level of readiness, improved in accordance with all operational (technical–technological, economic, energy, safety, quality, and environmental) requirements of machinery used in the mechanized operation of wells.

1. Object of the research:

The surface equipment complex of machinery used in the mechanized operation of wells and the issues related to achieving the 7th level of readiness.

2. Relevance of the work:

Balanced derrick units account for 70% of the surface mechanical complexes used in the oil production industry. The widespread use of balanced derricks faces several key shortcomings: small efficiency at low loads and high power losses, imperfect design of the reducer in the rotary and transmission mechanisms (low gear ratio, high metal consumption), impossibility of using high-speed electric motors, large mass requiring a heavy foundation, heavy loading of belt drives necessitating the use of multiple belts with uneven load distribution, leading to their rapid failure. These issues are considered the main deficiencies in the mechanical transmission of conventional rod-type well pumps.

Novelty of the task. Figure 1 shows the structural diagram of the wellhead equipment for the mechanized method of energy production (see Figure 1). A new surface equipment complex for machinery used in the mechanized operation of wells will be created, whose drive–transmission–rotary (motion–transmission–conversion) chain meets technical–technological, economic, energy, safety, quality, environmental, and other requirements of the operation process. The scientific basis for ensuring its 7th level of readiness will be developed.

Figure 1. Structure of the Surface Complex

Method and materials

Figure 2 shows a kinematic diagram of the wellhead equipment for a mechanized energy production method, modernized by the authors to the level of invention. The necessary theoretical and design studies were then conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the developed wellhead system, ensuring efficient energy production (see Figure 2).

At the modern stage of the oil production industry, it is a

pressing issue to create new, more advanced surface complexes for the mechanized operation of wells, featuring a transmission mechanism and kinematic pairs that reduce friction losses. These complexes should, first of all, ensure energy savings, reduce overall dimensions, increase reliability, and bring the movement of the rod’s suspension point—including its speed and acceleration—closer to theoretical laws. This problem inevitably requires the development of a new

surface equipment complex at the 7th level of readiness, improved in terms of technical-technological, economic,

energy, safety, quality, and environmental requirements, and optimized for consumer performance.

Figure 2. New Surface Complex

Figure 3 shows the loading diagram of the elements of the new complex developed, on the basis of which the ratios of the kinematic and dynamic parameters of the elemental composition of the developed complex were determined, which made it possible to bring it to the 7th level of development in accordance with international standards for assessing the readiness of equipment for its introduction to the market (see Figure 3). To this end, fundamentally new

transmission mechanisms have been developed to reduce the energy intensity of energy production using the developed wellhead system. Their capabilities have been substantiated using proposed ratios of design, kinematic, and dynamic parameters, combined into appropriate clusters, whose parameters are compatible in the proposed combinations and ensure energy efficiency during operation (see Figure 4).

Figure 3. Kinematic Diagram of the Complex

3. Objective of the work:

The objective is to develop the design of an innovative modular transmission complex, whose rotary mechanism is based on a rope–block–crank system, that allows efficient use of counterweights to save electrical energy, reduces the

weight of the surface complex, and significantly simplifies its construction. The work also aims to solve the problem crucial for ensuring the development of this complex at the 7th level of readiness.

Figure 4. Multi-Stage Transmission Mechanisms

Figure 5. Intellectual Document of Transmission Mechanisms

4. Conclusion:

For the first time, a new surface equipment complex for machinery used in the mechanized operation of wells will be created, whose drive–transmission–rotary (motion–transmission–conversion) chain meets technical–technological, economic, energy, safety, quality, environmental, and other requirements of the operation process. The scientific basis for ensuring its 7th level of readiness will be developed.

For this purpose:

- a relationship will be established between the input and output kinematic parameters of the complex's rotary chain mechanism.
- the possibilities for balancing cyclically varying loads will be determined.
- models will be created and evaluated to analyze dynamic forces arising in the load-bearing structural elements of the new multi-chain surface complex.
- based on the analysis of these forces, their metric dimensions will be justified, and the dimensional parameters of the complex will be defined.
- for each dimension in the created parametric set, a mechanism will be developed linking the motion regimes of the rod suspension point of the downhole pump unit to the

productivity of the well–tubing hydraulic system. At the same time, mechanisms for the efficient use of counterweights will be developed, which save electrical energy, allow control of the mass characteristics of the complex, and simplify structural design.

5. Results:

The existing surface equipment complexes of machinery used in mechanized well operation will be studied, and data on their design, manufacturing, installation, and operation will be systematized and analyzed.

Models for the efficient use of counterweights will be developed, ensuring the motion of the rod suspension point of the downhole pump unit follows a law closest to harmonic motion, saves electrical energy, allows control of the mass characteristics of the complex, and simplifies structural design.

A new surface equipment complex of the drive–transmission–rotary chain will be created, and a relationship will be established between the input and output kinematic parameters of the rotary chain mechanism, ensuring its 7th level of readiness.

The relationship between the motion regimes of the suspension point of the rod string in the downhole pump unit and the kinematic diagram of the new surface equipment

complex, consisting of the drive–transmission–rotary motion chain, will be investigated.

The relationship with the kinematic diagram of the new surface equipment complex will be investigated.

The possibilities for balancing cyclically varying loads will be determined based on conditions of equal loading in the drive chain of the new surface equipment complex and the absence of negative torque in the output shaft of the transmission chain.

Models will be created and evaluated to analyze the dynamic forces arising in the load-bearing structural elements of the new multi-chain surface complex. Based on this analysis, their metric dimensions will be justified, and the dimensional parameters of the complex will be determined.

For each dimension in the developed parametric set, a mechanism will be established linking the motion regimes of the suspension point of the rod string in the downhole pump unit to the productivity of the well–tubing hydrodynamic system.

Refined computational models, taking friction into

account, will be developed and solved for the gear transmissions of the package reducer in the transmission chain of the drive mechanism of the existing surface equipment complex used in mechanized well operation.

A new transmission chain, consisting of drive–transmission–rotary components that meet the technical–technological, economic, energy, safety, quality, environmental, and other requirements of the operation process, with high consumer performance, will be created for machinery used in mechanized well operation. Its development at the 7th level of readiness will be ensured.

The main parameters regulating the load-bearing capacity and performance of the mechanisms included in the drive–transmission–rotary chain of the new surface equipment complex for machinery used in mechanized well operation designed to meet technical–technological, economic, energy, safety, quality, environmental, and other operational requirements will be determined in relation to the productivity of the well tubing hydrodynamic system.

Figure 6. Indicators of the New Complex

By determining the required number of strokes of the rod suspension point, it will be possible to reduce the cost of service associated with high operational expenses for maintenance and repair of a surface complex that has achieved the 7th level of readiness, as well as to increase the intervals between repairs.

The production (5th level of readiness – Baku Worker Machine-Building Plant, TASC) and installation (6th level of

readiness – well No. 1043 at Absheronneft NQÇI on Pirallahi Island) of the new surface equipment complex for machinery used in mechanized well operation will create opportunities to assess all potential technical and technological errors. This, in turn, provides favorable conditions for making decisions to regulate and enhance the efficiency of the joint operation of its subsurface and surface components.

Figure 7. Equipment model

The implementation of the new surface equipment operation by up to 45%, confirming that this complex is of complex for machinery used in mechanized well operation will significant importance for the oil production industry. reduce the amount of electrical energy consumed during its

Table 1. Energy Consumption Table

Comparative analysis of standard beam pumping units and a beam pumping unit with a new structural design

Pumping unit model	Nominal load at the polished rod suspension point, kN	Polished rod stroke length, m	Torque on the gearbox output shaft, Nm		Gain in force, times	Energy savings
			Base version	Proposed version		
CKA2-0,6-250	20	0,6	2500	1427	1,75	43%
CKA3-1,5-710	30	1,5	7100	4221	1,68	41%
CKA4-2,1-1400	40	2,1	14000	8689	1,61	38%
CKA6-2,5-2800	60	2,5	28000	13000	2,15	54%
CKA8-3,0-4000	80	3,0	40000	19076	2,10	52%
CKA10-3,5-5600	100	3,5	56000	29832	1,88	47%
CKA12-3,0-5600	120	3,0	56000	30847	1,82	45%

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